

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Sparseness-Optimized Feature Importance for Time Series Classification

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ABSTRACT The literature reports a wide variety of attribution methods for explaining the predictions made by time series classification (TSC) algorithms. These post-hoc explanation methods span from model-specific to agnostic procedures that operate at different granularity levels. Despite their relative success, they often fail to generate sparse explanations, thereby increasing the cognitive overhead for experts seeking to isolate the most relevant features associated with model performance. Another limitation of segment-based explanation methods for TSC problems is that they do not allow any expert intervention. In this paper, we present an agnostic explainer termed Sparseness-Optimized Feature Importance (SOFI) that can be used to explain the predictions generated by any black-box TSC model. In practice, the explanation takes the form of a ranking of time series segments whose cumulative perturbation leads to fast degradation in model performance. Those segments should ideally be provided or defined by experts to ensure that explanations are meaningful and aligned with domain knowledge. As a second contribution, we mathematically demonstrate that under the modularity assumption, the optimal segment ranking associated with SOFI is unique. If the modularity assumption is dropped, we prove that multiple segment importance rankings lead to the optimal model performance degradation. In our experiments, we study the effect of different strategies for computing time series segments and perturbation operators on the explanation results. Simulation results show that SOFI generates explanations that are equally robust, up to 16 times more faithful, and 1.4 times sparser than those generated by the state-of-the-art explainers used for comparison.

INDEX TERMS Theoretical optimality, time series classification, segment attribution, sparse explanations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Time series classification (TSC) [1], [2] has become a rapidly growing area in machine learning, with numerous methods being proposed regularly. Whether these approaches resort to basic statistics, such as histograms, or more advanced strategies, such as deep learning architecture, they tend to

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operate as black boxes. For example, ROCKET (Random Convolutional Kernel Transform) variants [3], [4] apply a large number of randomly generated convolutional filters to the input time series. Afterwards, they compute simple statistics (such as the proportion of positive values and the maximum value) from each filter output. Naturally, these random filters do not bear any meaning for the problem domain, and their purpose narrows down to extracting features used for classification purposes.

The need for explainable AI in TSC arises from the inherent complexity of time series data, which are frequently multivariate, irregular, and lack a structured representation [5]. These properties make the internal operations of predictive models difficult to interpret, since the relevant temporal dependencies and interactions across variables are often distributed and not directly observable. A further challenge concerns the level of granularity at which explanations must be provided, as global summaries of decision rules may obscure local temporal features that drive specific classifications, while fine-grained attributions can become fragmented and unintelligible. The tension between these requirements underscores the importance of designing explanation methods that can adapt to the structure of time series data and align with the interpretive needs of domain experts.

Explanations may take several forms, including rule-based descriptions, prototype-based representations, counterfactual analyses, as well as approaches grounded in attribution or ranking of problem features. In this context, attribution relies on numerical values assigned to features or regions to reflect their influence on the model output, whereas feature ranking produces an order of features according to relative impact without explicit importance values. Attribution methods, whether model-specific or model-agnostic, represent the most popular explanation strategy in the literature for interpreting machine learning models. In the context of TSC settings, these methods generate explanations by highlighting the contribution of different elements within the time series data to the model's predictions [6]. They can be organized into three primary categories based on their level of granularity, starting from the finest to the coarsest: time point-oriented, subsequence-oriented, and instance-oriented.

- Time point-oriented explainers emphasize the importance of specific, individual observations or time steps within the time series. These methods often adapt techniques like SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [7] or gradient-based attributions (e.g., Integrated Gradients [8]) to time series data. The resulting explanations are depicted as saliency maps that pinpoint the specific moments in the sequence that most influenced the classification outcome. This high-granularity approach is particularly useful for identifying transient events or anomalies, but can be noisy in long sequences.
- Subsequence-oriented explainers shift focus to time series segments rather than assigning relevance scores to isolated points [9], [10]. Common techniques include shapelet discovery, i.e., discriminative subsequences that represent class characteristics [11], [12]. This medium-granularity level balances detail with interpretability, making it suitable for detecting recurring motifs in domains like sensor data or financial trends.
- Instance-oriented explainers evaluate importance at the level of entire time series variables or features as a whole [13], [14], [15]. These methods frequently involve

counterfactual explanations or feature importance rankings that provide a broader view of which channels drive decisions. This coarser granularity is often useful for multivariate time series where inter-feature relationships matter more than temporal specifics.

Despite the progress made in the field, existing feature attribution procedures for TSC tasks fall short when it comes to three properties: *model-agnosticism*, *expert intervention*, and *explanation sparsity*. Firstly, while explainers are desired to be as model-agnostic as possible, many approaches resort to the classifier's underlying structure or training processes to compute the attribution scores. Secondly, explanation methods for TSC do not allow for the inclusion of any expert knowledge about the time series being explained. For example, cardiologists know well the relevant segments in an ECG signal, even when they do not know the role these segments play in the predictions made by a back-box model. The limitation reduces the meaningfulness of the generated explanations in real-world settings where domain knowledge is available. Finally, most existing explanation methods reported in the literature, if not all, fail in producing sparse explanations. This leads to the cognitive overhead of experts who seek to isolate the top factors leading to model prediction. In real-world settings, non-sparse explanations lack practical value as they are unable to isolate the minimum set of factors behind the model's decision process.

In this paper, we introduce Sparseness-Optimized Feature Importance (SOFI), an agnostic explainer for TSC that operates at a segment level and that can be applied to univariate and multivariate time series. The segments are expected to be meaningful for the problem domain and provided by experts, yet they can be obtained automatically using change-point time series segmentation algorithms if needed. Instead of producing attribution scores, SOFI produces a ranking of segments whose cumulative perturbation leads to fast degradation in model performance. Such fast degradation ensures that the explanation is sparse. As a result, we can isolate the minimum set of segments that lead to a change in the class assigned to the time series by the classifier. It is fair to mention that the rationale of building a ranking of features minimizing the area under the marginalization-performance curve was first proposed by Grau and Nápoles [16] in the context of tabular pattern classification. As a second contribution, we will mathematically prove that under the modularity assumption, the optimal segment ranking that minimizes SOFI's loss function is unique and can be obtained by a greedy segment selection. If the modularity assumption is dropped, we will prove that there will be many segment importance rankings leading to the optimal model performance degradation. The numerical simulations compare the performance of SOFI against other state-of-the-art explainers, including model-specific procedures based on gradients. Moreover, we study the effect of different time series perturbation operators on the explanation results and conclude that the right operator choice is problem-dependent. The simulations show that SOFI is practically and statistically

superior to the other approaches in terms of explanation sparsity and robustness.

Compared with existing explainers for TSC models, SOFI brings the following innovations:

- SOFI is a declarative explainer that focuses on maximizing explanation quality rather than computing scores to determine the relevance of each segment in the classification process. In other words, SOFI determines what properties the explanations should have and optimizes the segment ranking to accomplish them, without the need for any proxy for segment scoring (e.g., the strength of gradients associated with each segment).
- SOFI makes no assumptions about the segments beyond the fact that they are determined *a priori*, for example, given by domain experts or computed automatically through segmentation. However, when building symbolic explanations, the number of segments trades off precision, since more segments allow for detailed explanations, against significance, since fewer segments yield clearer insights. The optimization procedure that powers SOFI balances these two properties by ensuring that the explanation is precise while involving a minimal set of meaningful time series segments.
- Our paper provides formal conditions for the existence and uniqueness of the optimal segment ranking. Under modularity, the solution is unique and obtainable via greedy selection. Without modularity, multiple rankings can yield equivalent optimal degradation.

The remainder of this paper goes as follows. Section II reviews relevant attribution-like explanation methods for TSC, while Section III presents the proposed algorithm and the theoretical analysis that studies the existence and uniqueness of the optimal segment ranking. Section IV studies the effect of the perturbation operators on the explanation results and compares SOFI with state-of-the-art methods. Section V concludes the paper, discusses some limitations, and provides future research directions to be explored.

II. RELATED WORK

Let $\mathbf{x} = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ be a time series, where m denotes its length. This paper focuses on real-valued univariate time series where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^m$. A time series dataset \mathbf{D} is a set of tuples (\mathbf{x}_k, y_k) , where y_k is the label associated with the k -th time series. Hence, $\mathbf{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_1, y_1), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_n, y_n)\}$, where n is the number of time series instances in this dataset. Labels are encoded by a nominal variable $y_k \in \mathbb{N}$ and form a finite set $\mathbf{Y} = \{y_1, \dots, y_c\}$, where c is the number of classes. Moreover, we will assume that $f(\mathbf{x})$ is the classifier computing the decision class for \mathbf{x} , and that each time series is associated with a single label that does not change in time.

For model-specific explanation methods, the black box $f(\cdot)$ is fixed and the explanations generated depend on its structure. In contrast, in model-agnostic methods, $f(\cdot)$ is treated as a black box producing class labels. In post-hoc

methods, the explanation model is independently created after $f(\cdot)$ is built. In addition, in the following subsections, we will use $\Gamma(f, \mathbf{x})$ to denote an explanation mechanism. The outcome of $\Gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ varies depending on the method. In the analysis presented below, we focus on feature attribution methods (producing relevance scores or rankings), as they are the most pertinent to the scope of our proposal.

A. TIME SERIES POINT-BASED EXPLANATIONS

Time series point-level explanations are determined for each time point t_i in a given time series \mathbf{x} . Therefore, their final operating (post-hoc) mode can be denoted as a function such that $\Gamma(f, \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{r}$, where $\mathbf{r} = \{r_1, \dots, r_m\}$ is the vector of relevance scores associated with \mathbf{x} . It is worth mentioning that the relevance vector \mathbf{r} can be computed for each time series in the dataset, that is $\forall_{\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbf{D}} \Gamma(f, \mathbf{x}_k) = \mathbf{r}_k, \mathbf{r}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$.

In the literature, there exists a wide range of approaches that produce point-based explanations. The most common strategy is to adapt methods from other classification tasks, e.g., feature attribution at the level of pixels in image classification. These methods use gradients [8], [17], propagate relevance signals through the network structure [18], [19], use perturbations [7], [20] or local surrogates [21] for computing the feature attribution. In the context of time series, instead of generating saliency maps overlaid on image pixels, these explainers visualize feature attributions associated with each time point in the series [22], [23].

In particular, gradient-based attribution methods estimate the contribution of each input feature by analyzing how sensitive the model's prediction is to small perturbations in that feature. Formally, they rely on the gradient of the model's output with respect to the input, which quantifies how a local change in the feature value affects the prediction score. A simple approach is to compute the raw gradient of the class score with respect to the input features [24]. Since gradients may be unstable or vanish, an alternative is to weight them by the input values themselves, as in Gradient \times Input [17], which can highlight features with both high activation and strong influence on the output. Integrated Gradients [8] extend this idea by accumulating gradients along a path from a baseline input (commonly the zero vector or a black image) to the actual input, ensuring that the attribution satisfies desirable axioms such as sensitivity and implementation invariance. SmoothGrad [25] addresses gradient noise by averaging attributions across multiple noisy copies of the input, thereby producing smoother and more visually interpretable importance maps. Variants of these methods differ in how they stabilize gradients, enforce axiomatic properties, or handle non-linear effects, but all share the central principle of using the derivative of the output with respect to the input as the foundation of feature attribution.

Perhaps the most popular model-agnostic approach is SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [7], which approximates the computationally demanding Shapley values.

It computes all feature contributions to the final prediction for a given instance. In addition, SHAP values are additive, which means that their sum equals the difference between the expected output for the dataset and the actual output for a given input. The study in [26] compared various model-agnostic XAI methods in time series and concluded that SHAP works robustly for all black-box models tested.

Another common model-agnostic method is Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) [21], which uses a surrogate linear model for approximating a local explanation. A local surrogate model aims to determine what would happen if a given feature value changes [27]. To do that, it generates a semi-synthetic dataset of perturbed time series samples in a neighborhood of the original instance of interest. The authors in [28] also segmented the series uniformly before adding random noise to the points. However, in both cases, the generation of random perturbations often leads to unrealistic synthetic instances.

Perturbation-based methods constitute another important family of explanation techniques for time series classifiers. PERT [29] is a model-agnostic approach that derives feature importance from the number of perturbations required to flip a model's prediction. Similarly, FIT [30] measures prediction sensitivity using counterfactual perturbations rather than random ones. Feature occlusion [31], which identifies the most influential input regions by masking those that induce the largest change in the classifier's output, is the most widely used representative of this family and has become a standard baseline in comparative studies.

B. TIME SERIES SEGMENTS-BASED EXPLANATIONS

We denote this mode of operations as $\Gamma(f, [t_i, t_{i+j}]) = r_i$, which means that the time series segment $[t_i, t_{i+j}]$, $j > 0$ was evaluated with the score r_i . The formula entails that the attribution calculation concerns an entire segment. Specific methods differ in their operations, as they can be model-specific or model-agnostic, global, or local. There are also differences in the segmentation strategies.

Let us first mention the use of intrinsically interpretable classifiers, such as decision trees or linear models, to produce explanations. Existing methods in this group segment the time series into equally sized bins, averaging their values, and encoding these segments in a discrete space. Approaches using this rationale were presented, for example, by Lee et al. [10] and Fauvel et al. [9]. However, operating with fixed-length segments is unlikely to be aligned with domain-relevant segments, leading to suboptimal explanations that fail to align with the domain knowledge.

By definition, the entire family of classifiers that detect the so-called *shapelets* can be the basis for classification and simultaneous explanation. In the domain of TSC, a shapelet can be roughly defined as a segment of a time series that is deemed characteristic (i.e., it encodes a pattern). However, there is no agreed-upon definition of the mathematical or statistical properties that a segment must satisfy to be

considered a shapelet [32]. Several examples of classifiers that extract shapelets to classify the data were proposed by Wang et al. [11] and Hu et al. [12]. Furthermore, some authors use the term "patch" to refer to a segment that is the basis for generating explanations. This terminology is used, for example, by Mercier et al. [33] or Das et al. [34]. Both papers utilizing this terminology focus on model-specific methods for neural network architectures.

Another example of a model-specific post-hoc method is Time Series eXplanation (TSXplain) [35], which is tailored to neural networks. It generates explanations by segmenting the time series and computing statistical descriptors (such as mean, variance, and higher-order moments) for each segment. These descriptors are then correlated with the network's learned representations to identify the temporal regions that contribute most to the final prediction. This approach bridges raw input data and latent features, which provides interpretable summaries of temporal importance while remaining dependent on the underlying model architecture.

C. TIME SERIES-BASED EXPLANATIONS

The third approach analyses the importance of a time series as a whole (i.e., as a sequential instance). Such models, when operating in a post-hoc manner, can be denoted as $\Gamma(f, \mathbf{x}_k) = \mathbf{L}_k$, where \mathbf{L}_k is the generated explanation.

In a multivariate setting, predictive dependencies among time series can be studied, as done in Long Short-Term Cognitive Networks (LTCNs) [36], [37]. This recurrent neural network relies on prior knowledge while providing a feature-importance measure. Other methods extract statistical features [38] or more complex features describing the series [39], [40] to be used as factors for interpretation in the classification afterward. However, the actual understandability of feature-based methods strongly depends on the interpretability of the adopted features and the target users [6].

The literature reports other series-level explanation methods that generate explanations using prototypes. In a nutshell, a prototype in this context is a representative time series, somewhat similar to a shapelet. However, while a shapelet is typically a subsequence of a series, a prototype can be generated after clustering several time series instances. Alternatively, such generation can be performed employing encoder networks, as in Ming et al. [41] and Zhang et al. [42]. Finding the nearest neighbor to the instance being explained [14] or combining distance measures with shapelets [15] have also proven to be effective strategies.

III. SPARSENESS-OPTIMIZED FEATURE IMPORTANCE

In this section, we introduce the SOFI explainer for TSC problems, which produces sparse explanations in the form of a ranking of time series segments. In terms of explanation granularity, SOFI provides a reasonable balance between precision and significance, which is a primary requirement for generating meaningful explanations.

Unlike other post-hoc explainers in the literature, SOFI can operate with segments that carry a well-defined semantics for the time series being explained. These segments are either defined by a domain expert or extracted with a segmentation algorithm as a preprocessing step. For example, in an ECG signal (see Figure 1), segments are known and studied for relevant diagnostic criteria. Providing explanations based on isolated time series points or alternative segments would only generate distrust among medical experts, who expect simpler explanations based on those segments. Therefore, the authentic purpose of explanations must be to generate insights into why segments are associated with the black-box outcome. If the expert knowledge is not available, SOFI can operate on automatically discovered segments without hindering its effectiveness.

FIGURE 1. Example electrocardiogram signal with known relevant segments. The vertical axis represents electrical amplitude (in mV), and the horizontal axis represents time (in seconds). Key segments and intervals are labeled, including the P wave, PR segment, QRS complex, ST segment, T wave, U wave, PR interval, and QT interval.

Even if the state-of-the-art explainers could operate with meaningful segments defined by domain experts, they would still fail to provide sparse explanations. This happens because neither the black boxes nor the explainers are generally optimized for isolating the smallest set of characteristics driving the decision. To overcome this issue, SOFI produces a ranking of segments that maximizes the sparsity of the explanation without compromising its faithfulness to the black-box model. Such a rationale can be applied to any machine learning model in an agnostic manner.

A. RANKING OPTIMIZATION

Let $\mathbf{S} = \{\mathbf{x}^{(1)} = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{b_1}\}, \mathbf{x}^{(2)} = \{t_{b_1+1}, \dots, t_{b_2}\}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(l+1)} = \{t_{b_l+1}, \dots, t_m\}\}$ represent the set of segments defined by experts or obtained via an automatic segmentation procedure, where $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$ denotes the i -th segment. In a nutshell, we can view segments as subsequences of consecutive time points limited by breakpoints $\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_l\}$.

The optimization step that powers the SOFI explainer is to find a ranking of segments $\Pi = \{\pi_1 \leq \pi_2 \leq \dots \leq \pi_{l+1}\}$

maximizing the sparseness of the explanation, with $\pi_i \in \mathbf{S}$ being the segment ranked in the i -th position. The optimal ranking reflects the conditional relevance of each segment when classifying the time series. The term conditional means that the relevance of each segment is not independent but relative to the relevance of other segments.

More explicitly, we define the conditional model performance after perturbing the first i segments in the ranking as:

$$g(\pi_i | \Pi_{<i}) = f(\mathbf{x}, \Pi_{<i} \cup \{\pi_i\}) \quad (1)$$

where $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A})$ represents the probability assigned by the black-box model to the originally predicted class after perturbing the set $\mathbf{A} \subseteq \mathbf{S}$. We note that the model's outputs $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A}) \in [0, 1]$ for all $\mathbf{A} \subseteq \mathbf{S}$.

When working with time series data, perturbation operations must be handled with caution. Prior studies [43], [44], [45] have shown that common point-wise strategies, such as replacing values with zero, mean, inverse, or noise, do not consistently degrade predictive performance. In some cases, the perturbed time series retain information useful for classification. To address this issue, we treat the perturbation type as a hyperparameter and select the most effective strategy for each instance. Besides the classic replacements, we propose a local search method to determine an optimal constant leading to the more aggressive performance degradation. In this method, each segment is perturbed with a constant series that maximally reduces the probability of the correct class, starting from the mean series of the opposite classes in the training set. This approach increases the likelihood of inducing a class change after modifying only a few segments, or at most after all segments are perturbed.

To generate sparse explanations, SOFI computes the points $\{(0, g(\emptyset)), (1, g(\pi_1 | \Pi_{<1})), \dots, (l+1, g(\pi_{l+1} | \Pi_{<l+1}))\}$ such that $g(\emptyset) = f(\mathbf{x}, \emptyset)$ gives the model's performance for the original series. Eq. (2) shows the objective function to be maximized by a discrete optimizer,

$$\max \rightarrow \mathcal{D}(\Pi) = \mathcal{L}(\Pi) - \mathcal{M}(\Pi), \quad (2)$$

such that

$$\mathcal{M}(\Pi) = \sum_{i=0}^l \frac{g(\pi_i | \Pi_{<i}) + g(\pi_{i+1} | \Pi_{<i+1})}{2} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}(\Pi) = \sum_{i=0}^l \frac{g(\pi_i | \Pi_{<i}^{\leftarrow}) + g(\pi_{i+1} | \Pi_{<i+1}^{\leftarrow})}{2} \quad (4)$$

where we define $\Pi_{<0} = \emptyset$ and $\Pi_{<l+2} = \mathbf{S}$. In this formulation $\Pi^{\leftarrow} = \{\pi_{l+1} \leq \pi_l \leq \dots \leq \pi_1\}$ represents the reverse permutation of Π .

The proposed objective function maximizes the degradation score $\mathcal{D}(\Pi)$, defined as the difference between two performance degradation curves that measure the drop in class probability as segments are perturbed. The area under the MoRF (Most Relevant First) curve, denoted $\mathcal{M}(\Pi)$, is obtained by sequentially perturbing segments from most to

least relevant according to Π . Conversely, the area under the LeRF (Least Relevant First) curve, denoted $\mathcal{L}(\Pi)$, is obtained by perturbing segments from least to most relevant according to Π^{\curvearrowright} . In TSC tasks, an explanation is considered sparse if the MoRF curve shows a steep decrease, which indicates that perturbing the top-ranked segments is sufficient to substantially degrade the model's prediction. The LeRF curve should remain relatively flat while marginalizing unimportant segments and suffer a drop when relevant segments are altered. In this case, a well-formed LeRF curve indicates a faithful explanation, meaning that the segment importance aligns with the behavior of the underlying black-box model. Therefore, a large degradation score, quantified by the area between these two curves, serves as a reliable indicator of faithfulness and sparsity of the feature attribution.

Finding a permutation of segments leading to optimal sparse explanations involves solving a combinatorial optimization problem. In this paper, we resorted to the Hill Climbing (HC) algorithm to optimize the objective function due to its efficiency. Although HC does not guarantee reaching the global optimum, it often produces good enough solutions in a reasonably short execution time. In our approach, each candidate solution is represented as an integer sequence encoding the indices of the segments. To ensure valid permutations, duplicate values are not allowed by restricting solutions to arrangements of the first $l + 1$ integers. Algorithm 1 summarizes the key steps of our HC-based search, and Figure 2 shows a blueprint of the SOFI explainer.

The proposed SOFI explainer takes as input a time series instance to be explained, the segments defined by domain experts, and the trained black-box model. The ranking is initialized by perturbing each segment individually and measuring the corresponding drop in prediction probability (the rationale behind this strategy will be introduced in the next subsection). Segments are then sorted in descending order of their individual impact, which serves as the starting point for the optimization process. The maximum number of iterations and the patience parameter regulate the duration of the HC search. Notice that any perturbation strategy from the literature may be employed during the perturbation step of the algorithm. The output is a feature-attribution ranking that identifies the segments most important for the prediction of the instance, according to the black-box model.

Algorithm 2 formalizes the local search procedure that serves as an alternative to a static perturbation strategy. It relies on the golden section line search to identify a constant value that minimizes the prediction probability of the original label. The method explores the interval defined by training-set statistics, progressively narrowing it down by comparing candidate values positioned according to the golden ratio. Once the interval becomes sufficiently small or the iteration limit is reached, additional candidate values, including the minimum, the maximum, the mean, and a uniform random value of the series, are evaluated together with the midpoint of the interval. The best candidate is

Algorithm 1 SOFI Explainer for Time Series Classifiers

- 1: **Input:** Time series instance \mathbf{x} , trained black-box classifier f , segmentation set \mathbf{S}
- 2: **Parameters:** patience p , maximum number of iterations for optimizer max_iter
- 3: Initialize baseline probability $g(\emptyset) \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x})$
- 4: **For each segment** $\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \in \mathbf{S}$:
- 5: Create perturbed instance $\mathbf{x}' \leftarrow \text{perturb}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^{(i)})$
- 6: Compute probability drop $\Delta_i \leftarrow g(\emptyset) - f(\mathbf{x}')$
- 7: **End For**
- 8: Initialize best ranking Π by sorting segments in descending order of Δ_i
- 9: Initialize best evaluation $\mathcal{D}(\Pi) \leftarrow -\infty$
- 10: Initialize candidate ranking $\Pi^* \leftarrow \Pi$
- 11: Initialize $counter \leftarrow 0$ ▷ number of iterations without improvement
- 12: **Repeat until** max_iter or $counter \geq p$:
- 13: Initialize the perturbed instance $\mathbf{x}' \leftarrow \mathbf{x}$
- 14: Initialize the baseline performance $g(\emptyset) \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x})$
- 15: **For feature** π_i **in** Π^* **and segment** $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$ **in** \mathbf{S} :
- 16: $\mathbf{x}' \leftarrow \text{perturb}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}^{(i)})$
- 17: Evaluate the effect in the prediction $g(\pi_i) \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}')$
- 18: **End For**
- 19: Calculate $\mathcal{D}(\Pi^*)$ based on Eq. (2)
- 20: **If** $\mathcal{D}(\Pi^*) > \mathcal{D}(\Pi)$:
- 21: Update best evaluation $\mathcal{D}(\Pi) \leftarrow \mathcal{D}(\Pi^*)$
- 22: Update best candidate $\Pi \leftarrow \Pi^*$
- 23: Reset $counter \leftarrow 0$
- 24: **Else**
- 25: Increment $counter \leftarrow counter + 1$
- 26: **End If**
- 27: Generate new candidate Π^*
- 28: **End Repeat**
- 29: **Return:** Feature attribution ranking of segments Π

then used to replace the target segment with a constant perturbation.

Before moving to the theoretical analysis, it would be convenient to elaborate on the conceptual difference between SOFI and other explainers. Existing perturbation-based explanation methods operate in a procedural fashion that establishes how segments are scored according to some criterion that serves as a proxy for segment importance (e.g., strength of gradients associated with each segment). After scoring, segments are ranked and evaluated using MoRF and LeRF curves to quantify explanation sparsity and meaningfulness, respectively. In contrast, SOFI is conceptually rooted in declarative programming. It defines *what* properties the explanations should have and optimize the segment ranking to accomplish them, without the need for any proxy for segment scoring. This approach separates the *what* from the *how*, allowing flexible optimization strategies like Hill Climbing to produce high-quality ranking-based explanations.

FIGURE 2. Blueprint of the SOFI explainer. SOFI produces explanations as a ranking of segment importance for time-series classification tasks.

B. EXISTENCE AND UNIQUENESS OF THE OPTIMALLY SPARSE RANKING

In this section, we analyze the mathematical properties of segment rankings generated by the proposed SOFI explainer. We establish the conditions for the existence of an optimal ranking of segments under the minimization of the area under the MoRF curve $\mathcal{M}(\Pi)$. Due to the path-dependent nature of the conditional performance, the uniqueness of the optimal ranking cannot generally be guaranteed. Moreover, we discuss the conditions that lead to non-uniqueness and the implications for the optimization problem.

Theorem 1 (Existence): There exists at least one optimal ranking that yields the maximum possible sparse explanation $\Pi^* \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{S})$.

Proof: Since $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{S})$ is finite with $|\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{S})| = (l + 1)!$ and $\mathcal{M}(\Pi)$ is a real-valued function defined for all $\Pi \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{S})$, \mathcal{M} attains a minimum by the extreme value principle on finite sets. This gives a trivial proof. \square

Algorithm 2 Perturbation Procedure Using Golden Section Line Search

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1: Input: Instance  $\mathbf{x}$ , segment  $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$ 
2: Global: training set statistics ( $v_{\min}, v_{\text{mean}}, v_{\max}$ ), classifier  $f$ 
3: Initialize perturbed instance  $\mathbf{x}' \leftarrow \mathbf{x}$ 
4: Compute label  $y = \arg \max_c f(\mathbf{x}') [c]$ 
5: Set search interval  $[a, z] \leftarrow [v_{\min}, v_{\max}]$ 
6: Define golden ratio  $\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ 
7: Compute interior points:
8:  $c \leftarrow z - \frac{z-a}{\varphi}, d \leftarrow a + \frac{z-a}{\varphi}$ 
9:  $f_c \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow c)[y], f_d \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow d)[y]$ 
10: for  $t = 1$  to  $T_{\max}$  do
11:   if  $|z - a| < \epsilon$  then
12:     break
13:   end if
14:   if  $f_c < f_d$  then
15:      $z \leftarrow d, d \leftarrow c, f_d \leftarrow f_c$ 
16:      $c \leftarrow z - \frac{z-a}{\varphi}, f_c \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow c)[y]$ 
17:   else
18:      $a \leftarrow c, c \leftarrow d, f_c \leftarrow f_d$ 
19:      $d \leftarrow a + \frac{z-a}{\varphi}, f_d \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow d)[y]$ 
20:   end if
21: end for
22: Evaluate candidates:
23:  $s_{\min} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow v_{\min})[y]$ 
24:  $s_{\max} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow v_{\max})[y]$ 
25:  $s_{\text{mean}} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow v_{\text{mean}})[y]$ 
26:  $s_{\text{rand}} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow \mathcal{U}(v_{\min}, v_{\max})) [y]$ 
27:  $s_{\text{mid}} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \leftarrow \frac{a+z}{2}) [y]$ 
28: Select best perturbation value
29:  $v^* \leftarrow \arg \min \{s_{\min}, s_{\max}, s_{\text{mean}}, s_{\text{rand}}, s_{\text{mid}}\}$ 
30: Replace  $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$  in  $\mathbf{x}'$  with  $\{v^*, v^*, \dots, v^*\}$ 
31: Return: Perturbed instance  $\mathbf{x}'$ 

```

Moving forward, the function $g(\pi_i | \Pi_{<i})$ depends not only on the segment π_i but also on the set $\Pi_{<i}$ of segments that have been perturbed before it. This path dependence implies that the same segment π_i may contribute differently to the function \mathcal{M} depending on its position in the ranking and the specific identity of the segments that precede it.

Theorem 2 (Non-Uniqueness): The optimal ranking of time series segments Π^* minimizing \mathcal{M} is not necessarily unique. Multiple distinct segment rankings may yield the same minimal value of \mathcal{M} .

Proof: This is a consequence of the path dependence of g and the fact that the function \mathcal{M} is a sum over the entire permutation. It is possible that two different rankings Π and Π' produce performance curves that are different pointwise but yield the same value of \mathcal{M} . If there exist two distinct segments s and t and a set $\mathbf{A} \subseteq \mathbf{S} \setminus \{s, t\}$ such that:

$$f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A} \cup \{s\}) = f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A} \cup \{t\}) \quad \text{and}$$

$$f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{B} \cup \{s\}) = f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{B} \cup \{t\}) \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{B} \supseteq \mathbf{A}$$

then any swap of s and t in any permutation leaves \mathcal{M} invariant. This provides a concrete structural source of non-uniqueness. \square

The optimization problem posed by SOFI is a combinatorial permutation problem with an objective function that depends on the entire sequence of perturbations. Without strong assumptions on the black-box model f , such as additivity of segment contributions or context independence, we cannot guarantee the uniqueness of the optimal ranking.

While uniqueness cannot be guaranteed in general, next, we will establish a sufficient condition under which the optimally sparse segment ranking is unique.

Definition 1 (Modular set function): The set function f is modular if there exists a non-negative map $c : \mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that for all $A \subseteq \mathbf{S}$:

$$f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A}) = f(\mathbf{x}, \emptyset) - \sum_{s \in \mathbf{A}} c(s).$$

Theorem 3 (Uniqueness under modularity): If f is modular, then the optimal ranking Π^* is unique up to permutation of segments with equal $c(s)$. Moreover, Π^* is the ranking that orders the segments in non-increasing order of $c(s)$, so it can be computed using a greedy approach.

Proof: Under modularity, the conditional performance after perturbing the first i segments can be computed as follows:

$$g(\pi_i | \Pi_{<i}) = f(\mathbf{x}, \emptyset) - \sum_{j=1}^i c(\pi_j).$$

Consequently, the \mathcal{M} function becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(\Pi) &= \sum_{i=0}^l \frac{g(\pi_i | \Pi_{<i}) + g(\pi_{i+1} | \Pi_{<i+1})}{2} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^l \frac{\left(f(\mathbf{x}, \emptyset) - \sum_{j=1}^i c(\pi_j) \right) + \left(f(\mathbf{x}, \emptyset) - \sum_{j=1}^{i+1} c(\pi_j) \right)}{2} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^l \left(f(\mathbf{x}, \emptyset) - \sum_{j=1}^i c(\pi_j) - \frac{c(\pi_{i+1})}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This can be rewritten as follows:

$$\mathcal{M}(\Pi) = (l+1)f(\mathbf{x}, \emptyset) - \sum_{k=1}^{l+1} \left((l+1-k) + \frac{1}{2} \right) c(\pi_k).$$

To minimize $\mathcal{M}(\Pi)$, we must maximize the weighted sum $\sum_{k=1}^{l+1} w_k c(\pi_k)$, where the weights $w_k = (l+1-k) + \frac{1}{2}$ are strictly decreasing with k . This is achieved by assigning the largest $c(s)$ to the largest weight, which corresponds to the earliest position in the ranking.

Therefore, the optimal ranking is obtained by sorting segments in non-increasing order of $c(s)$. If all $c(s)$ are distinct, this ranking of time series segments is unique. If some segments have equal $c(s)$, they can be permuted arbitrarily without affecting the value of \mathcal{M} .

Moreover, under modularity, the greedy choice at each time series segment simplifies because the following holds:

$$f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A} \cup \{s\}) = f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A}) - c(s).$$

Since $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A})$ is fixed for the current step, minimizing $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A} \cup \{s\})$ over $s \in \mathbf{R}$ is equivalent to maximizing $c(s)$ over $s \in \mathbf{R}$, where \mathbf{R} denotes the set with the remaining segments. Thus, the greedy algorithm selects the segment with the largest remaining $c(s)$ at each iteration.

This process iteratively constructs the segment ranking by selecting, at each position k from 1 to n ($n = l + 1$), the segment s from the remaining set \mathbf{R} that maximizes $c(s)$. The first iteration selects the segment with the globally maximal $c(s)$ from the full set \mathbf{S} . Each subsequent iteration k selects the segment with the maximal $c(s)$ from the progressively smaller set R containing the $n - k + 1$ segments not yet chosen. This procedure systematically builds the ranking $\Pi_g = (\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_n)$ where π_1 has the largest decrement, π_2 the next largest, and so forth, resulting in a sequence ordered in strict non-increasing order of $c(s)$. As such, this non-increasing order is the optimal ranking Π^* that maximizes explanation quality. Therefore, $\Pi_g = \Pi^*$. \square

Algorithm 3 shows the steps for computing the greedy ranking. If the optimal ranking is unique (i.e., all $c(s)$ are distinct), there are no ties in the argmax selections. As proven in Theorem 3, it ensures that the greedy algorithm produces a unique output matching Π^* .

Algorithm 3 Greedy Ranking Algorithm

- 1: Initialize the perturbed set $\mathbf{A} \leftarrow \emptyset$
 - 2: Initialize the remaining segments $\mathbf{R} \leftarrow \mathbf{S}$
 - 3: **for** $k \leftarrow 1$ to n **do**
 - 4: $\pi_k \leftarrow \arg \min_{s \in \mathbf{R}} f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A} \cup \{s\})$
 - 5: Append π_k to Π_g
 - 6: $\mathbf{A} \leftarrow \mathbf{A} \cup \{\pi_k\}$
 - 7: $\mathbf{R} \leftarrow \mathbf{R} \setminus \{\pi_k\}$
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **return** $\Pi_g = (\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_n)$
-

The greedy algorithm runs in $O(n^2)$ time (e.g., through repeated scans for the maximum) or in $O(n \log n)$ with sorting or pre-heapification. Since n is small in practice, efficiency is not a concern. In our approach, the greedy ranking serves as the initial solution. If modularity holds, which is straightforward to verify, the optimal ranking will be unique and returned by the greedy search procedure (Theorem 3). Otherwise, the solution space may contain several optimal rankings (Theorem 2), and HC will find one of them by refining the greedy solution until convergence (e.g., until the patience criterion is met). It should be stressed that modularity is a strong assumption that rarely holds in practice, as the effect of perturbing a segment generally depends on which other segments have already been perturbed.

IV. SIMULATIONS AND EXPERIMENTS

The experimental evaluation is organized into three parts. We first illustrate the rationale of SOFI on a well-known time series classification task to provide an intuitive example of how the method generates sparse explanations. Next, we use a collection of 15 benchmark datasets to conduct a sensitivity analysis of the perturbation strategy and the patience parameter. Finally, we compare SOFI against five state-of-the-art methods for computing feature attributions in time series classification. For all datasets, a preprocessing step for segmentation annotation was performed.

A. METHOD ILLUSTRATION

To illustrate SOFI's inner workings, we use the Cylinder-Bell-Funnel (CBF) dataset [46], one of the most widely studied simulated problems in time series classification. In this dataset, samples are generated from standard Gaussian noise with an added class-specific shift term. The three decision classes correspond to distinct shape types, namely: *cylinder*, *funnel*, and *bell*. As the benchmark time series datasets do not provide expert knowledge regarding their segmentation, we apply a preprocessing step based on structural break detection, also known as change point detection. In this illustration, we will use the Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) algorithm [47], [48]. Figures 3(a) to 3(c) present all time series instances for each class along with their corresponding mean series for visualization purposes only. These instances exhibit clear, easily recognizable patterns, which allow straightforward verification of explanations.

In all simulations conducted in this section, we employ the InceptionTime architecture [49] as the black-box model, which is widely regarded for its strong performance in TSC tasks [50]. Nonetheless, notice that the choice of the classifier does not influence SOFI's operation as long as it delivers high-quality predictions, yet it might influence the explanation results. InceptionTime models are trained using the predefined UCR splits [51], a batch size of 256, and the AdamW optimizer with cosine annealing learning rate scheduling, for up to 500 epochs. To avoid overfitting, we apply early stopping with a patience of 25 epochs, based on a validation set comprising 20% of the training data, stratified by class. Given the simplicity of the CBF dataset, InceptionTime correctly classifies 99% of the test samples.

Once the classifier is trained, we select an instance, predict its class, and execute SOFI to produce a feature-attribution explanation. The optimization process of SOFI is set to run for a maximum of 100 iterations. At each iteration, a new candidate solution is generated by modifying a single position in the current permutation. To ensure that the experiments can be reproduced, a fixed random seed is used throughout the process. Figures 3(d) to 3(f) show the resulting feature attribution as a saliency map over randomly chosen time series examples from each class. The procedure returned the following permutations for the investigated time series: ($s_2 \leq s_0 \leq s_1 \leq s_3$) for the class *cylinder*, ($s_3 \leq s_2 \leq s_0 \leq s_1 \leq$

$s_5 \leq s_4$) for the class *bell*, and ($s_2 \leq s_5 \leq s_4 \leq s_3 \leq s_0 \leq s_1$) for the class *funnel*.

For the first time series, we note that s_2 is selected as the most relevant segment, which contains several values with a constant high trend. This is indeed the most distinguishing feature for this class, as the other two classes do not exhibit relatively long, constant trend behaviors in these time steps. For the second time series, s_3 is the most determinant segment, followed by s_0 to s_3 where we observe a linear increasing trend of value change. These patterns indeed distinguish this class well from the other two classes. Concerning the last time series, s_2 and s_5 are regarded as the most important segments. When visually comparing the characteristics of samples from the classes *cylinder*, *bell*, and *funnel*, we can observe that the instances belonging to the class *funnel* typically involve a spike, while instances of the class *bell* are characterized by small and slow increases.

Figure 4 illustrates the optimization trajectory of SOFI for the representative instance of the class *funnel*. Subfigures show the MoRF and LeRF curves corresponding to the permutation selected at a given iteration of the algorithm. The y-axis is measured as the probability of the predicted decision class for the instance being explained. The point denoted as B represents the baseline probability of the instance when no perturbation has been applied yet. The initial prior ranking serves as the baseline, from which the algorithm progressively explores alternative segment permutations.

Table 1 reports the performance metrics across all iterations of the same optimization process. For each permutation tested, we present the areas under the MoRF and LeRF curves, the normalized degradation score, and the sparsity rate. Lower AUC-MoRF values and higher LeRF-AUC values are preferred. The degradation score (DS) is defined as the signed difference between AUC-LeRF and AUC-MoRF [44], [52]. A positive DS indicates meaningful feature attributions, as MoRF perturbations affect predictions more than LeRF, while DS values close to zero suggest non-discriminative attributions. Negative DS values indicate incorrect attributions, as LeRF perturbations have a stronger impact than MoRF. For comparability, we normalize the DS metric by dividing it by the maximum possible area between the two curves. Table 1 also reports the sparsity rate as the ratio between the number of segments that must be perturbed to produce a different class (i.e., the sparsity point) and the total number of segments. The sparsity rate ranges from zero to one, where lower values indicate greater sparseness.

The simulation results show that the algorithm starts from a prior configuration with low degradation power but quickly identifies higher-quality rankings. The final solution, reached at iteration 27, attains the best DS (0.510) with a sparsity rate of 0.333, meaning that only one-third of the segments are required to generate a faithful explanation. Overall, the reader can observe that the MoRF and LeRF curves differ both in shape and separation across iterations. This behavior results from the stochastic search procedure used to optimize the segment ranking. The search is driven by random local

FIGURE 3. Illustration of explanation results produced by SOFI for the CBF dataset. Subfigures (a)–(c) display all time series instances (light gray) in the dataset and their corresponding class-wise mean series (blue). Subfigures (d)–(f) show the relevant segments obtained by SOFI for randomly selected instances of each class.

TABLE 1. Performance metrics of SOFI across optimization iterations on a CBF instance.

Iteration	Permutation	AUC MoRF	AUC LeRF	Normalized DS	Sparsity Rate
PRIORS	[2, 3, 0, 5, 1, 4]	3.196	3.362	0.033	0.667
0	[4, 3, 0, 5, 1, 2]	3.520	1.865	-0.331	0.667
1	[4, 3, 0, 5, 1, 2]	3.520	1.865	-0.331	0.667
2	[2, 0, 3, 5, 1, 4]	2.942	3.146	0.041	0.667
3	[2, 4, 3, 5, 1, 0]	2.256	3.822	0.313	0.333
4	[0, 4, 3, 5, 1, 2]	3.494	2.054	-0.288	0.667
5	[2, 4, 3, 5, 0, 1]	2.268	3.836	0.313	0.333
6	[0, 4, 3, 5, 2, 1]	3.433	2.431	-0.200	0.667
7	[5, 4, 3, 2, 0, 1]	2.520	3.127	0.121	0.500
8	[4, 2, 3, 5, 0, 1]	2.668	3.835	0.233	0.333
9	[2, 0, 3, 5, 4, 1]	2.883	3.124	0.048	0.667
10	[0, 4, 3, 5, 2, 1]	3.433	2.431	-0.200	0.667
11	[2, 0, 3, 5, 4, 1]	2.883	3.124	0.048	0.667
12	[2, 4, 3, 5, 1, 0]	2.256	3.822	0.313	0.333
13	[2, 5, 3, 4, 0, 1]	1.891	4.104	0.442	0.333
14	[2, 5, 3, 0, 4, 1]	2.328	4.151	0.365	0.333
15	[3, 5, 2, 4, 0, 1]	2.808	3.363	0.111	0.667
16	[2, 1, 3, 4, 0, 5]	2.929	3.132	0.041	0.833
17	[2, 5, 4, 3, 0, 1]	1.418	3.966	0.510	0.333
18	[2, 4, 5, 3, 0, 1]	1.585	3.775	0.438	0.333
19	[2, 4, 5, 3, 0, 1]	1.585	3.775	0.438	0.333
20	[3, 5, 4, 2, 0, 1]	2.608	2.676	0.014	0.500
21	[4, 5, 2, 3, 0, 1]	2.272	3.575	0.261	0.500
22	[2, 5, 0, 3, 4, 1]	2.057	4.111	0.411	0.333
23	[4, 5, 2, 3, 0, 1]	2.272	3.575	0.261	0.500
24	[2, 5, 4, 1, 0, 3]	1.377	3.879	0.500	0.333
25	[0, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]	3.060	3.134	0.015	0.667
26	[3, 5, 4, 2, 0, 1]	2.608	2.676	0.014	0.500
FINAL	[2, 5, 4, 3, 0, 1]	1.418	3.966	0.510	0.333

changes to the current permutation, so intermediate solutions are neither required to be optimal nor progressively closer

to the final one. At these stages, the algorithm may traverse structurally diverse rankings, producing heterogeneous curve

FIGURE 4. Optimization trace of SOFI for one instance of the CBF dataset. Each subfigure shows the MoRF (blue) and LeRF (brown) curves associated with the permutation selected at different stages of the algorithm. The process begins from the prior ranking (a), explores alternative permutations across intermediate iterations (b–h), and converges to the final ranking (i), which provides the sparsest explanation consistent with the classifier’s prediction.

patterns. A parallel can be drawn with stochastic gradient descent, where randomness in update steps leads to irregular trajectories and apparent jumps in the objective landscape before convergence. In both cases, stochasticity supports exploration of the search space, while the final iterations reflect convergence toward a strong solution where explanatory patterns become stable and coherent.

B. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

For the remaining experiments in this section, we use publicly available TSC datasets [51], which come with predefined train, validation, and test splits. These problems are widely used for evaluating the performance of time series classifiers [50]. For each dataset, we train an InceptionTime model using the same hyperparameter configuration as outlined for the CBF dataset in the previous subsection.

Table 2 summarizes statistical properties of the selected datasets along with the classifier’s performance. The first group of columns describes dataset characteristics, including the number of classes, test set size, time series length, and the number of segments identified by the segmentation annotation. The variation in time series length and number of classes across datasets contributes to the robustness of our simulations. The last two columns report the InceptionTime accuracy (computed as the proportion of correctly classified test instances) and the macro F1 score (computed as the unweighted mean of the class-specific F1 scores across all classes) on the test set, which are consistent with previously reported results for these datasets [50].

First, we evaluate the performance of different segmentation algorithms for detecting breakpoints as a preprocessing step on the results of SOFI, measured in terms of normalized DS. Regarding SOFI hyperparameters, we allow 10, 20, and

TABLE 2. Details of the benchmark TSC datasets and InceptionTime performance. In the table, c is the number of classes, k is the number of time series in the test set, m is the time series length, and $|S|$ is the number of segments.

ID	Dataset	c	k	m	$ S $	Accuracy	F1 score
D01	Adiac	37	391	176	9	0.754	0.725
D02	ArrowHead	3	175	251	10	0.754	0.749
D03	BeetleFly	2	20	512	24	0.800	0.792
D04	CBF	3	900	128	5	0.999	0.999
D05	Car	4	60	577	15	0.867	0.864
D06	ChlorineConcentration	3	3840	166	7	0.729	0.715
D07	ECG200	2	100	96	5	0.890	0.887
D08	ECG5000	5	4500	140	6	0.940	0.932
D09	Fish	7	175	463	13	0.977	0.977
D10	FordA	2	1320	500	41	0.953	0.953
D11	FordB	2	810	500	41	0.798	0.796
D12	GunPoint	2	150	150	5	1.000	1.000
D13	Lightning2	2	61	637	10	0.803	0.803
D14	Plane	7	105	144	9	1.000	1.000
D15	Wafer	2	6154	152	6	0.998	0.998

30 iterations without progress and evaluate several perturbation strategies: mean, random, local search, maximum, and minimum. Results are averaged across all datasets. We compare PELT [47], Dynamic Programming [48], Binary segmentation [53], Bottom-up segmentation [54], and Window-based segmentation [48]. PELT identifies change points by solving a globally optimal penalized cost minimization problem using a pruning strategy. Dynamic Programming computes the exact optimal segmentation by evaluating all admissible partitions for a given number of change points. Binary segmentation follows a greedy recursive strategy that iteratively splits the signal at the most significant detected change point. Conversely, Bottom-up segmentation starts with a fine-grained initial partition and progressively merges adjacent segments according to a cost criterion. Sliding Window segmentation detects change points by comparing statistics computed over adjacent sliding windows along the time series. For methods that require specifying the number of change points, this value was set to five.¹

FIGURE 5. Average normalized DS obtained with different segmentation algorithms across all datasets.

Figure 5 summarizes the impact of the segmentation strategy on the normalized degradation score. PELT achieves

¹For all methods, we use the default settings provided by the `ruptures` Python package [48].

the highest degradation scores on average, indicating that segmentations obtained through a global optimization criterion lead to more informative segments and more effective explanations. Binary segmentation follows, with consistently high scores but larger variability across datasets. Dynamic Programming and Bottom-up segmentation obtain intermediate degradation scores, while Window-based segmentation performs worst overall. Despite some overlap in variability, the relative ordering of methods is clear. It should be noted that lower-quality or locally driven segmentations do not result in erratic or inflated scores. Instead, degradation scores consistently decrease, reflecting reduced explanatory power rather than confidently misleading importance assignments. Based on these results, we select PELT as the preprocessing segmentation step for the remaining experiments in this paper.

Next, we evaluate the effect of the patience hyperparameter on the quality of the solutions obtained by the SOFI explainer. Figure 6 presents the distribution of normalized DS values across instances of each dataset when allowing 10, 20, and 30 iterations without progress. The gray shaded regions illustrate the variability in DS values for each dataset, while the marker colors symbolize the best-performing perturbation strategy. The results show that the mean perturbation most frequently yields the best DS values, yet alternative strategies such as local search or extreme-value perturbations perform better in some datasets or specific instances.

To provide statistical support for this claim, we employ the pairwise Wilcoxon signed rank test [55]. The test evaluates paired performance differences and compares each perturbation strategy against the mean perturbation baseline. In addition, we correct the Wilcoxon p -values using Holm's procedure [56] and compute Cohen's d [57] statistic as a measure of effect size, which gives the magnitude of the difference in DS values between the tested strategies. Table 3 reports that the mean perturbation shows a statistically significant difference from the maximum strategy with a medium effect size ($d=0.73$) in favor of the control method. However, the differences observed for

FIGURE 6. Effect of the patience hyperparameter (10, 20, and 30 iterations without progress) on the DS values obtained by SOFI. Markers are colored according to the best-performing strategy for each dataset: mean (blue), random (red), local search (brown), maximum (green), and minimum (orange). Shaded areas give the DS variability across instances.

minimum, random, and local search perturbation strategies are not statistically significant after correction. This evidence reinforces the observation from the figure that although the mean perturbation is generally the most reliable choice, there are instances where alternative perturbations achieve better results. Hence, adaptively selecting the perturbation method on a per-instance basis is preferable to using a fixed strategy for all cases.

TABLE 3. Pairwise Wilcoxon tests comparing perturbation strategies against the mean perturbation. Holm correction is applied to the Wilcoxon p -values, while Cohen’s d is employed to quantify the effect size.

Method	Cohen’s d	Wilcoxon	Holm’s	Hypothesis
max	0.726	0.013	0.05	Reject
min	0.562	0.041	0.106	Fail to Reject
local	0.591	0.035	0.106	Fail to Reject
random	0.423	0.121	0.121	Fail to Reject

Increasing the patience parameter from 10 to 30 does not yield systematically better solutions, which confirms that more iterations without progress does not improve the overall optimization outcome. To further examine this, we analyze runtime² as a function of the granularity of the explanations, measured by the number of segments per instance.

The results in Figure 7 report average runtime across all instances of all datasets, with the x-axis grouping instances according to increasing segmentation. As expected, runtime increases with the number of segments; however, this effect is considerably more pronounced for higher patience values. In particular, patience 30 requires up to two times more runtime than patience 10 for instances with a high number of segments. Importantly, for a practical number of segments (between 1 and 20, highlighted by the gray area in the figure), SOFI converges to a solution in under 40 seconds. It suggests that the method is computationally efficient at

²All experiments were executed on a computer with a 3.4 GHz Quad-Core Intel Core i7 processor and 32 GB RAM.

FIGURE 7. Average runtime across all instances of all datasets as a function of the explanation granularity, for each value of patience. The gray area highlights the practical range of segmentation (1)–(20).

realistic levels of granularity and scalable to larger datasets. Since larger patience values do not provide performance gains while substantially increasing runtime, we set patience to 10 for the remainder of the experiments.

C. COMPARISON AGAINST STATE-OF-THE-ART METHODS

In this experiment, we compare the performance of SOFI with state-of-the-art feature attribution methods for time series classification. We considered four gradient-based methods, namely, Gradients (GR) [24], Integrated Gradients (IG) [8], SmoothGrad (SG) [25], and Gradient SHAP (GS) [7], as well as the perturbation-based method Feature Occlusion (FO) [31]. The combination of UCR Archive datasets, InceptionTime as the classification model, and these feature attribution methods has been employed in prior explainability evaluation studies [44], [58], making our experimental setting directly comparable to earlier works.³

For comparability, we align the attribution scores produced by all explainers with the segments identified by PELT by averaging their point-wise scores within each segment.

³For all experiments, we use the InceptionTime and feature attribution implementations from the `tsxai` Python package available at <https://github.com/gregorbaer/class-perturbation-effects>

TABLE 4. Average normalized DS for each method across datasets.

ID	FO		GRAD		GS		IG		SG		SOFI	
	mean	std	mean	std								
D01	0.042	0.095	-0.002	0.095	0.059	0.073	0.048	0.074	0.016	0.079	0.134	0.121
D02	0.102	0.205	-0.105	0.226	0.084	0.215	0.129	0.218	0.100	0.153	0.510	0.159
D03	0.014	0.267	0.038	0.253	0.008	0.222	0.061	0.239	0.098	0.122	0.584	0.092
D04	0.035	0.296	0.096	0.279	0.073	0.340	0.084	0.328	0.193	0.260	0.438	0.148
D05	0.182	0.206	0.189	0.240	-0.006	0.153	-0.036	0.220	0.076	0.261	0.595	0.162
D06	0.317	0.307	0.310	0.254	0.223	0.262	0.217	0.255	0.321	0.280	0.552	0.192
D07	-0.136	0.425	-0.014	0.369	-0.144	0.409	-0.120	0.400	0.154	0.334	0.713	0.114
D08	-0.291	0.458	0.296	0.532	-0.263	0.525	-0.250	0.473	0.520	0.386	0.863	0.147
D09	0.202	0.194	0.266	0.151	0.210	0.256	0.202	0.213	0.132	0.178	0.514	0.185
D10	0.081	0.132	0.002	0.140	0.072	0.102	0.077	0.096	0.019	0.119	0.450	0.204
D11	-0.077	0.394	0.015	0.281	0.010	0.474	-0.002	0.470	-0.067	0.376	0.697	0.095
D12	0.276	0.511	0.021	0.349	0.129	0.447	0.174	0.420	-0.304	0.462	0.653	0.197
D13	0.011	0.317	0.157	0.286	-0.226	0.204	-0.184	0.215	-0.002	0.388	0.599	0.134
D14	0.284	0.288	0.349	0.196	0.302	0.307	0.309	0.318	0.389	0.158	0.627	0.112
D15	-0.140	0.590	0.284	0.356	-0.183	0.602	-0.139	0.613	0.365	0.256	0.737	0.117

If segments provided by domain experts were available, the same procedure would be applied to these methods. For perturbation strategies, we retained the best-performing strategy for each instance across all methods, as established in the previous experiment. To ensure balanced class representation, we compute feature attributions on a stratified sample of 100 test instances. Attributions are generated with respect to the predicted class label and restricted to correctly classified instances. This procedure also maintains computational feasibility when working with large datasets.

Table 4 presents the mean and standard deviation of the normalized DS values for each method evaluated across all benchmark datasets. The results show that SOFI achieves the highest scores across all datasets, often by a substantial margin. For instance, across datasets D02, D03, D05, D07, D08, and D15, SOFI outperforms the nearest competitor by more than 0.3 DS points, indicating a clear improvement in explanation quality. Gradient-based methods (GRAD, IG, GS, and SG) exhibit relatively unstable behavior, with mean scores close to zero and, in several cases, negative, which means that their attributions can be misaligned with the true discriminative segments. Feature Occlusion (FO) generally performs better than gradient-based methods, but still lags far behind SOFI in terms of both average score and consistency. Moreover, the standard deviations for SOFI are moderate compared to those of other methods, suggesting that its performance is not only superior on average but also more robust across different datasets.

Aiming to assess the significance of the observed differences, we conducted pairwise statistical tests between SOFI and each baseline method (Table 5). The Wilcoxon signed-rank tests yield p -values below $1.0E-4$ in all cases, which remain significant after Holm's correction for multiple comparisons. This suggests that the improvements achieved by SOFI are statistically significant across datasets. More importantly, the effect sizes measured by Cohen's d are large in all cases, ranging from 1.82 (FO) to 2.55 (GRAD). This confirms that the observed differences are not only statistically significant but also practically meaningful.

TABLE 5. Pairwise comparisons of methods in terms of normalized DS using SOFI as the control method. Holm correction is applied to the Wilcoxon p -values, while Cohen's d is employed to quantify the effect size.

Method	Cohen's d	Wilcoxon	Holm	Hypothesis
FO	1.82	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
GRAD	2.55	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
GS	1.96	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
IG	1.96	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
SG	2.04	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject

Table 6 reports the average sparsity rate across datasets. The results show that SOFI produces sparser explanations than all baseline methods since it attains lower sparsity rates. For example, in datasets D03, D07, D08, D11, and D13, SOFI achieves values below 0.15, whereas competing methods typically require perturbing between 30% and 60% of the features to alter the predicted class. This suggests that SOFI can identify a smaller and more informative subset of features responsible for the model's decision, which produces explanations that are compact. While baseline methods sometimes reach moderate sparsity (e.g., FO on D01 and GRAD on D05), their performance is highly inconsistent across datasets. In contrast, SOFI maintains low sparsity rates with relatively small standard deviations.

To validate these observations, we performed pairwise statistical tests between SOFI and each baseline method (Table 7). The Wilcoxon signed-rank tests produce p -values below $1.0E-4$ in all comparisons, which remain significant after applying Holm's correction. This confirms that the lower sparsity rates achieved by SOFI are statistically significant across datasets. The effect sizes measured by Cohen's d are all large and negative, ranging from -1.58 (SG) to -1.98 (IG). It translates into a large reduction in the proportion of features required to change the predicted class.

Figure 8 illustrates the fold-change superiority of the SOFI explainer over the baseline methods in terms of normalized DS (left) and sparsity rate (right). In terms of the normalized DS metric, SOFI shows a substantial advantage, being more

TABLE 6. Average sparsity rate for each method across datasets.

ID	FO		GRAD		GS		IG		SG		SOFI	
	mean	std										
D01	0.123	0.045	0.181	0.131	0.122	0.033	0.122	0.033	0.157	0.110	0.119	0.040
D02	0.393	0.246	0.526	0.266	0.453	0.310	0.409	0.290	0.367	0.230	0.212	0.172
D03	0.327	0.334	0.274	0.327	0.328	0.326	0.343	0.330	0.271	0.318	0.063	0.028
D04	0.497	0.241	0.481	0.242	0.474	0.239	0.465	0.240	0.445	0.270	0.349	0.197
D05	0.266	0.234	0.230	0.180	0.372	0.330	0.367	0.318	0.306	0.268	0.120	0.095
D06	0.347	0.352	0.304	0.310	0.383	0.345	0.402	0.341	0.344	0.352	0.248	0.257
D07	0.511	0.234	0.547	0.251	0.544	0.249	0.533	0.252	0.440	0.219	0.221	0.070
D08	0.680	0.254	0.441	0.261	0.653	0.263	0.646	0.249	0.307	0.219	0.188	0.054
D09	0.264	0.244	0.235	0.204	0.255	0.237	0.253	0.217	0.348	0.272	0.131	0.113
D10	0.557	0.391	0.651	0.311	0.568	0.374	0.554	0.384	0.640	0.318	0.318	0.307
D11	0.579	0.308	0.529	0.324	0.431	0.353	0.423	0.335	0.598	0.319	0.098	0.090
D12	0.537	0.306	0.648	0.278	0.569	0.278	0.573	0.264	0.758	0.253	0.341	0.179
D13	0.415	0.264	0.309	0.262	0.512	0.245	0.483	0.242	0.363	0.266	0.123	0.043
D14	0.342	0.222	0.290	0.182	0.328	0.240	0.320	0.241	0.271	0.153	0.198	0.105
D15	0.552	0.241	0.349	0.186	0.591	0.250	0.577	0.251	0.379	0.127	0.226	0.077

FIGURE 8. Fold-change comparison of other methods with respect to SOFI in terms of normalized DS and sparsity rate.

TABLE 7. Pairwise comparisons of methods in terms of sparsity rate using SOFI as the control method. Holm correction is applied to the Wilcoxon p -values, while Cohen’s d is employed to quantify the effect size.

Method	Cohen’s d	Wilcoxon	Holm	Hypothesis
FO	-1.71	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
GRAD	-1.72	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
GS	-1.97	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
IG	-1.98	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject
SG	-1.58	6.10E-05	3.05E-04	Reject

than 3.5 times better than SG and GRAD, over 8.7 times better than FO, more than 11.3 times better than IG, and over 16 times better than GS. As for the sparsity rate, SOFI maintains a clear advantage, achieving more than 1.3 times better sparsity than SG and GRAD, and over 1.4 times better sparsity than the IG, FO, and GS methods.

Additionally, we evaluate explanation robustness by assessing the stability of SOFI rankings under small variations in the input space. For each correctly classified test instance x_i , we identify its nearest neighbor x_i^{NN} in the test set using a Euclidean distance on the standardized raw time series. Let $\Pi(x_i)$ and $\Pi(x_i^{NN})$ denote the ranked lists of segments produced by SOFI for these two instances. Robustness is quantified as the similarity between these

rankings using Rank-Biased Overlap (RBO) [59], which emphasizes agreement among the most relevant segments. We employ the extrapolated version of RBO to account for finite-length rankings and set the parameter $p = 0.8$, corresponding to an expected evaluation depth of approximately five segments. The overall robustness score is computed by averaging this similarity across all instances and is defined as:

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{x_i \in \mathcal{C}} \text{RBO}(\Pi(x_i), \Pi(x_i^{NN})), \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{C} denotes the set of correctly classified instances. A higher robustness score indicates that locally similar series have similar explanation rankings.

Table 8 reports the mean and standard deviation of the robustness scores for each attribution method across datasets. The results indicate that while SOFI does not always achieve the highest robustness values, it performs comparably to state-of-the-art methods. For example, SG exhibits slightly higher robustness on some datasets, whereas GRAD always achieves lower robustness than other methods. The statistical tests presented in Table 9 reflect these moderate differences, with only the comparison against GRAD being statistically significant. In contrast, the pairwise tests against FO, GS, IG,

FIGURE 9. MoRF curves for randomly selected instances associated with SOFI (blue) or other explainers (gray area). The star marker symbolizes the sparsity point for SOFI where the predicted decision class by the black box changes. Blank spaces appear near the sparsity point in almost every example, with a few exceptions where at least one other explainer matches SOFI’s performance. Moreover, the shaded areas provide insights into the quality of explanations for state-of-the-art models (the wider the shaded area, the greater the variability among explanations).

FIGURE 9. (Continued.) MoRF curves for randomly selected instances associated with SOFI (blue) or other explainers (gray area). The star marker symbolizes the sparsity point for SOFI where the predicted decision class by the black box changes. Blank spaces appear near the sparsity point in almost every example, with a few exceptions where at least one other explainer matches SOFI’s performance. Moreover, the shaded areas provide insights into the quality of explanations for state-of-the-art models (the wider the shaded area, the greater the variability among explanations).

TABLE 8. Average robustness for each method across datasets.

ID	FO		GRAD		GS		IG		SG		SOFI	
	mean	std										
D01	0.881	0.125	0.645	0.189	0.945	0.084	0.893	0.110	0.907	0.148	0.962	0.142
D02	0.692	0.213	0.691	0.166	0.848	0.141	0.839	0.152	0.897	0.117	0.816	0.278
D03	0.428	0.183	0.426	0.176	0.400	0.222	0.417	0.206	0.524	0.212	0.384	0.099
D04	0.906	0.118	0.894	0.108	0.938	0.087	0.948	0.080	0.954	0.077	0.946	0.145
D05	0.726	0.175	0.616	0.152	0.887	0.095	0.857	0.122	0.860	0.106	0.764	0.212
D06	0.984	0.038	0.978	0.041	0.973	0.060	0.976	0.069	0.988	0.028	0.998	0.108
D07	0.891	0.109	0.815	0.134	0.917	0.095	0.926	0.085	0.881	0.119	0.924	0.196
D08	0.922	0.100	0.892	0.105	0.949	0.085	0.950	0.076	0.951	0.081	0.958	0.232
D09	0.890	0.115	0.749	0.160	0.874	0.109	0.871	0.106	0.827	0.119	0.714	0.185
D10	0.249	0.158	0.150	0.129	0.294	0.150	0.378	0.167	0.238	0.142	0.278	0.077
D11	0.266	0.179	0.138	0.098	0.263	0.155	0.297	0.161	0.245	0.165	0.279	0.082
D12	0.963	0.053	0.887	0.100	0.895	0.113	0.934	0.090	0.934	0.093	0.965	0.139
D13	0.643	0.168	0.551	0.135	0.698	0.167	0.705	0.164	0.715	0.165	0.626	0.166
D14	0.955	0.061	0.866	0.127	0.936	0.081	0.956	0.064	0.956	0.071	0.991	0.115
D15	0.977	0.053	0.935	0.083	0.980	0.051	0.982	0.053	0.975	0.056	0.997	0.008

TABLE 9. Pairwise comparisons of methods in terms of robustness using SOFI as the control method. Holm correction is applied to the Wilcoxon p -values, while Cohen’s d is employed to quantify the effect size.

Method	Cohen’s d	Wilcoxon	Holms	Hypothesis
FO	0.52	4.13E-02	1.65E-01	Fail to Reject
GRAD	1.33	3.05E-04	1.53E-03	Reject
GS	0.15	5.24E-01	1.00E+00	Fail to Reject
IG	0.06	9.34E-01	1.00E+00	Fail to Reject
SG	0.11	8.04E-01	1.00E+00	Fail to Reject

and SG produce corrected p -values above 0.05, indicating no significant difference in robustness. The effect sizes,

measured by Cohen’s d , are small to moderate, except for GRAD, which shows a large effect size.

It is important to note that this notion of robustness relies on the assumption that locally similar instances should produce similar explanations. While this assumption is common in the literature [60], especially for adversarial robustness [61], [62], robustness is not necessarily correlated with other explanation quality metrics such as faithfulness or sparsity. In other words, a method can produce highly robust explanations that are nevertheless incorrect, unfaithful, or overly complex. Moreover, this robustness measure does not account for the possibility of multimodal explanation spaces, where multiple distinct explanations for the same

instance may be equally plausible. This phenomenon, often referred to as the *Rashomon effect* [63], highlights inherent ambiguity in interpreting model decisions and illustrates the limitations of robustness as a standalone evaluation metric.

Finally, Figure 9 presents MoRF curves for sample instances of each dataset, comparing SOFI to other feature attribution methods. For visualization purposes, we group all other method MoRF curves in the gray area that they cover. The number of segments varies widely across datasets, ranging from 5 to 46, which allows us to assess SOFI's performance across series of different lengths and complexities. SOFI achieves earlier sparsity points and steeper degradation curves as indicated by the blank space between the curve and the area. Its advantage is particularly pronounced in datasets with longer series and a higher number of segments, such as FordA (D10), FordB (D11), BeetleFly (D03), or Fish (D09). Together with the statistical analyses, these figures illustrate that SOFI generates explanations that are both significantly more faithful and sparser than those produced by gradient-based and perturbation-based baselines.

To conclude the numerical analysis, it is worth commenting on deployment aspects and on the extent to which the observed behavior generalizes across classifier families. From a deployment perspective, SOFI can be integrated as a post-hoc analysis component in both offline validation workflows and operational settings. It is particularly suitable for model auditing pipelines and domain-specific applications such as clinical decision support, where domain experts can supply meaningful segments to align explanations with domain knowledge. In near-real-time or resource-constrained settings, SOFI's patience parameter allows a balance between explanation quality and computational demand. From a generalization perspective, the results obtained with InceptionTime are representative of a broader family of high-performing classifiers, since the explainer interacts only with output probabilities under controlled perturbations. However, this does not mean that SOFI explanations are invariant to the black box choice. Some classifiers aggregate evidence across many segments to support their decisions, which leads to less sparser explanations, whereas other classifiers focus on a small number of key segments, producing sparser explanations. These differences are a direct consequence of how models encode temporal information and should be interpreted as informative cues about model behavior.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, we have proposed a declarative post-hoc explanation method termed SOFI for TSC that operates in an agnostic manner. SOFI outputs a ranking of segments whose cumulative removal causes a sharp drop in model performance, rather than producing attribution scores. Since this drop enforces sparsity in the explanation, it allows us to determine the minimal set of segments that induce a change in the predicted class. These segments are either provided by experts or extracted automatically using change-point time series segmentation algorithms. Moreover, we proved

mathematically that under the modularity assumption, the optimal segment ranking that minimizes SOFI's loss function is unique and can be derived through greedy segment selection. When the modularity assumption does not hold, we demonstrate that multiple segment rankings can result in the same degradation of optimal model performance. To the best of our knowledge, the ability to generate sparse explanations using expert knowledge is a valuable feature of our proposal that is not provided by any other explainer.

The numerical simulations using real-world datasets allowed us to draw solid conclusions. Firstly, the PELT segmentation algorithm obtained the most informative segments in the benchmark data where domain knowledge is not available. Secondly, higher patience values are not necessary to obtain good quality explanations with SOFI. More importantly, no single time-series perturbation operator fits all cases, so the right one for each instance must be determined via grid search. This remark applies not only to SOFI but also to any procedure that implements time series perturbation for evaluation purposes. Thirdly, the comparative analysis shows that SOFI comfortably outperforms state-of-the-art explanation methods in terms of explanation faithfulness and sparseness. The performance differences were confirmed to be statistically significant (using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Holm correction) and to have practically relevant effect sizes (using Cohen's d). SOFI also achieved competitive results with state-of-the-art methods when measuring its non-adversarial robustness. Finally, SOFI reported the lowest sparsity rate, identifying a minimal set of segments explaining the label predicted by the classifier.

Despite SOFI's superiority compared to other explainers, there remain areas for improvement that open further research directions. Solving the associated optimization problem is time-consuming, and the HC optimizer can become trapped in local optima. In addition, the segment ranking produced by SOFI is cumulative, since the k -th segment is computed under the assumption that the previous $k - 1$ positions no longer influence the classifier predictions. As a result, the importance of each segment is conditional rather than independent of other time series segments. In this regard, we could modify SOFI to compute feature relevance across all possible feature subsets, while preserving its declarative nature.

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